

Recommended citation: Fernandes, C., Rocha, L., & Charles, B. (2017). Lifelong Learning for the Development of Industrially Oriented Engineering Skills: 4X4InSchools Project . In Quadrado, J. C., Bernardino, J., & Rocha, J. (Eds.), *Education Excellence for Sustainability. SEFI 45th Annual Conference* (pp. 731-739). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Azores, Portugal. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14698239.

4X4IS main objective is to bring youngsters closer to industry, believing that everyone can make a difference for individuals, countries and economic prosperity.

Conference Key Areas: Attractiveness of Engineering Education, Skills and Engineering Education, Continuing Engineering Education and Lifelong Learning

Keywords: Lifelong learning, Sustainability, Project 4x4IS; Industry

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays youngsters (their educational tutors and other stakeholders) have negative images and perceptions of the metal industry and industrially related careers, that tend to be dirty, heavy, noisy and physically exhausting. According to this global ecosystem, industry related careers, up to here, were not socially valued and were unattractive to young people searching for a future profession. It is recognized that the industrial sector is unable to inspire and motivate enough young people to enter engineering programs or technical training paths related to industry. Future predictions show a significant fall in meeting business and industrial needs [1 - 5]. According to previous studies youngsters' tend to choose "easier" paths and careers with another public image and recognition [6]. Various researchers have studied students' attitudes towards "industry", "science" and "technology". Researches show that youngsters often have stereotypical images and that those images impact their attitudes toward science, industry and technology [7-16]. It appears that if a youngster can see himself/herself in a career, then, the likelihood of that person persecuting an educational program to prepare him/her to that career increases [17].

This diminished interest in engineering, industry and industrial related careers has been long associated with several factors such as: perceptions and images of industry, lack of knowledge, lack of understanding the contribution of engineering for everyday life, teaching methods, curricula, mismatch between values and the way technical subjects are approached, career guidance, youngsters lack of understanding and appreciation for their potential future role in society [18-23].

"Young people need to see the point of it all. They especially want practical application (not just practical work). This might be learning about a job, developing personal skills, experiencing team work or having a subject explained to them in terms of its contemporary context" [23, p.2]. Youngsters need these divergent approaches to learning versus most schools' curriculum approaches. It's unquestionable that lifelong learning with all the associated strategies are central issues for the development of a capable workforce and productive countries.

The Royal Academy of Engineering predicts a shortfall of 200,000 qualified engineers in the UK by 2020 [24]. The skills shortage [1] is an ongoing challenge for the project. The project 4x4 in Schools addresses this issue and builds the skills and talent of young people aiming their future career paths.

Fig. 1. 4x4ISchools Project Logo

1 THE PROJECT 4X4 IN SCHOOLS

1.1 4x4 in schools

The Jaguar Land Rover's 4x4 Global Challenge is an annual competition for 11-19 years' olds to design and build a radio-controlled, four-wheel drive model vehicle that features Land Rover's all-terrain characteristics. Over the course of a school year, students research, design and manufacture their vehicle, and perform tests before they compete with teams from other schools at the competition stage. Jaguar Land Rover (JLR), and international partners provide guidance and support throughout the process, including visits to participants' schools and youth groups. An average of 116,000 young people participated in the challenge each season starting on 2015/16.

In the last semester of 2015, JLR launched the Land Rover 4x4 in Schools programme globally in partnership with various in-country coordinators, including Portugal. Teams from countries as far afield as Australia, United States of America or South Korea competed in their national challenge competitions and the best teams from 15 countries meet every year for the World Final.

The 4x4 Challenge is operated in partnership with the Institution of Engineering and Technology (IET), JCB Academy (JCB), Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics Education Coalition (STEM), DENFORD and several leading engineering and education organisations. Young people participating in the scheme can be accredited for their achievements through schemes such as CREST, ASDAN and the Duke of Edinburgh Award and the Arkwright Trust.

The base for the program design is the creation of an ecosystem that potentiates capabilities and competencies toward future industrial careers, anchoring strategies on collaborative learning, active learning [25-32] creative thinking, project based learning, among others.

1.2 4x4IS objectives

- The challenge is educational but also provides participants with the opportunity to experience something that is realistic, as well as relevant to the operations within industry.
- Provides an experience where students can develop and embed knowledge and skills which may be later required in further education or their chosen career.
- Is motivating, exciting, challenging and fun for both the students and adults involved.
- Provides young people with the opportunity to work as part of a team or independently to develop problem solving skills and techniques.

- Enables real-life engineers (STEM Ambassadors) to connect with the future of the industry by sharing their engineering knowledge, expertise, enthusiasm and commitment with students from a range of backgrounds.
- Provides an opportunity for students to learn and develop through participation in a hands-on practical experience.
- Enables young people to gain understanding and awareness of what engineering is, encouraging them to actively think about a technical career.
- Integrates subject knowledge from key areas of the curriculum with the wider agenda of work-related learning, enterprise, key skills and personal development.
- Enables young people to be recognised for their achievements through schemes such as CREST, ASDAN and The Duke of Edinburgh Award.

1.3 4x4IS activities

The teams have access to several support resources, such as on-line support or a designated JLR tutor, 3D engineering software, computer numerical control machines (CNC), 3D printing machines. There are well defined rules for the competitions (either regional, national or world) that the teams must comply if they want to attain with the purposed objective. The teams must take in account several items when designing, developing and materializing their projects:

1. Each team must contain a minimum of 3 to a maximum of 6 students, each one with defined roles (e.g. Team manager, marketing manager).
2. Use Computer Aided Design (CAD) software to produce their ideas and model it in three dimensions (3D).
3. Use several manufacturing technologies to produce their own 4x4 vehicle.
4. To manufacture the body shell each team must choose either to use technology available at the school/college or at a real manufacturing company as a sponsor.
5. Follow the specifications concerning several rules, each car body must have some electronic features such turn lights when the environment is dark, tilt sound when the vehicle has a lateral inclination.
6. Produce a design folder including initial ideas; design development and evidence of the developed work, maximum 20 pages (A3 size).
7. Develop partnerships. 4x4inschools teams are encouraged to develop partnerships and seek assistance from academic, businesses and industry throughout this engineering process. However, all aspects of this engineering and industry partnership should be represented in the team's portfolio. This includes CAD designs, electronics, and the creation/production of the portfolio, which should remain the responsibility of the students in the team.
8. Prepare and deliver a 10 minutes' verbal presentation on their work with or without visual aids.
9. Learn all skills by self-learning methods or by seeking help from partners referred in item.

Fig. 2: 4x4inschools track

For the youngsters' teams these are complex projects, for so, they are reminded about some considerations such as:

- Resources: CAD/CAE packages help them to draw and to develop their ideas in 3D. As with most drawing packages, it takes time to learn how to use the software. CNC and 3D printing machines allow youngsters to see the project take “body” but the technology use must be studied and applied with caution. Wind/smoke tunnels allow youngsters to see the scientific aerodynamic principles and test them.
- ICT tools: the resources used are complex, and so are the results to be achieved, and the ways to support self-learning. ICT tools allows youngsters to manage their time and learning in more efficient ways. They can communicate and share doubts, help each other, have access to privileged material, and see real case studies, alongside with the JLR tutor support.
- Research: Teams are asked to investigate existing 4x4 car designs to find out the latest developments occurring in the world of 4-wheel drive design. Concentrate research on areas that could help teams, for example, gears, car body shell design, and try to apply the principles to the team ideas and in-hands projects.
- Testing: teams may want to consider testing a variety of car designs, or car parts to evaluate their performance in pass the obstacles.
- Manufacturing considerations: Rookie teams' have access to a beginner 4x4inschools Kit which is constituted by simple radio-controlled vehicle, but teams need to change at least the body shell and upgrade the electronics. Professional teams can build their own vehicle from zero.

Fig. 3: World final 2016

2 THE PORTUGUESE EXPERIENCE

2.1 4x4 IS Portugal

The cooperation between JLR and the Portuguese Technological Centers started in 2015, and it was organized two national finals. The project was developed in a consortium and the experience was obtained from similar projects for sensitize young students for Industry and Technical careers and related study areas. The consortium is a partnership with eight Portuguese Technological Centers spread in the Portuguese territory, from north to south.

Until the beginning of 2017 the consortium organized two national finals where 14 teams participated each year. It was possible to promote several immersion sessions directed at high schools (42 schools) encompassing more than 45.000 students. For the season 2016/017 it's already ongoing work with 14 teams' and its foreseeable to make aware of the project and its objectives approximately 120.000 youngsters.

For the season 2015/16 the challenge actively engaged 87 young people, 78 males and 9 females with ages from 13 to 19. More than 50% of those with ages between 15 and 16 years old. The global activities within the project encompassed 38.388 young students, for the season 2015/16.

Table 1. Season 2015/16 demographic data

Targets	Schools	Students	Aware
Planned	15	90	15.000
Reached	18	87	23.388

Table 2. Season 2015/16 students by age group

Age	%
13	3,4%
14	10,3%
15	10,3%
16	25,3%
17	25,3%
18	20,7%
19	4,6%

Every year since the beginning it has been organized a National Final with the aim of selecting the best team for representing Portugal in the World Finals. Depending on getting extra financial support or sponsorship, it could be possible to select a second team to go to the World Championship, and provide teams in the two levels of the competition (beginner and professional).

Since the first time the Portuguese teams faced the challenge the perceptions were very good from the different national and international stakeholders. The youngsters differentiated on the resilient way that obstacles were faced and dealt with – e.g. technical and economic. All international rules 4x4inschools for the selection of the best teams were applied in the Portuguese Final and in the World final. The teams have permanent support from JLR tutor, technological centres, schools and teachers, among others, to manage their efforts during school time and free time aiming to the

accomplishment of the project objectives without compromising academic achievement. As ongoing work the 4x4 IS Portugal team is conducting a longitudinal study, that started on the season 2015/16 aiming to assess perceptions and future training and development choices along with professional paths.

3 CONCLUSIONS

4X4 in Schools self-learning approach, supported by JLR and in-country partners, showed that it is very important for youngsters to apply their knowledge, skills and proficiency to tasks with an overall perceived meaning and using several different means (distance support, face to face meetings, collaborative work, sharing and developing knowledge through communities of practice) simulating as close as possible real industrial settings. And on the other hand, the contents and the final product with metal industrial relevance make youngsters aware of the impact that individual skills have on a wider project development and the results.

The authors believe that youngsters individually and has a team can be “trendsetters” who set their own learning and development paths and strategies. This concept points to the importance of e-learning, with all technological tools provided, in informal and non-formal learning has a mean for individual and group skill development towards sustainable development.

Young students need to experience “scenarios” in a hands-on approach with active learning strategies, to contextualize opportunities that the Metal Industries, the car industry and the industrial sector in general can provide. Making the linkage of the importance of technical and industrial related paths not only to individual fulfilment but also for the promotion of a sustainable industry contributing for the re-industrialization and for prosper countries and/or regions.

4 ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors wish to acknowledge the support of Engineering in Motion and Jaguar Land Rover. The project results would not have been possible without funding from the JLR ‘Inspiring Tomorrow’s Engineers’ Programme, and the Portuguese Technological Centres. This paper reflects the perspectives and experience of the authors.

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